

FORMATION OF OXYGEN COMPLEXES ON CHARCOAL

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Surface oxygen complexes on charcoal come into existence during or within a few minutes of the formation of the charcoal, and extend themselves rapidly on exposure to oxygen but, gradually on exposure to air, to the same limiting value. The presence of moisture has no effect. Ageing in limited supplies of air produces slow and restricted effects. The amount of complex decomposing into CO₂ decreases with increase in the carbonisation temperature, while that, decomposing into CO appears to be more or less independent of the carbonisation temperature. The base-neutralising capacity of charcoal is almost equivalent to the amount of CO₂ evolved on degassing the same at 1000°.

It is well known that almost all types of charcoals and activated carbons are covered by oxygen complexes (Lowry and Hulett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1408; Barrer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1261; Dewey and Lefforge, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1932, **24**, 1045; Lawson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, **32**, 473; Anderson and Emmett, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1947, **51**, 1308), the nature and composition of which vary with the treatment given to the sample (Schilow *et al.*, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **149A**, 211; **150A**, 31; King, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1489; Lepin, *Physikal. Z. Sowjetunion*, 1933, **4**, 282). The influence of these complexes on the adsorption of vapours, acids and bases has formed the subject matter of several publications (King and Lawson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, **30**, 1094; Dubinin and Zaverina, *J. Phys. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1947, **21**, 1373; McDermot and Arnell, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 492; Weller and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 4155; Bruns *et al.*, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, **63**, 286). It is generally believed that these complexes increase the capacity of charcoal to take up vapours and alkalis but decrease its capacity to adsorb acids.

Lowry (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 824) has pointed out that oxygen is slowly picked up by charcoal 'irreversibly' even at the room temperature. The recent work of Puri *et al.* (*Soil Sci.*, 1953, **75**, 209) also indicates that oxygen complexes are formed on exposure of charcoal to air or oxygen at ordinary temperatures. It is of interest to know how far these complexes exist on charcoal at the time of its formation and how far do they extend on exposure (at room temperature) to oxygen and air under different conditions. The present work was undertaken with these objectives in view.

EXPERIMENTAL

Charcoals were prepared by carbonisation of pure recrystallised cane sugar and coconut shell at temperatures varying from 350° to 600° in a Pyrex glass vessel placed in a heat-lagged nichrome coil for uniform electrical heating. The current was controlled with a Variac transformer.

The time of heating for the carbonisation varied between 30 and 90 minutes depending upon the carbonisation temperature. The smaller the temperature, the longer was the time allowed. The charcoals were immediately transferred to wide trays

and allowed to cool. The time required for this purpose was 10 to 15 minutes. The samples were split into four different groups, each weighing about 15 g. They were allowed to age under different conditions. One group was sealed in half-pound bottles; the second, spread in wide trays, forming 1 cm. thick layers, was exposed to air in a closet in which no foreign vapour or fumes could enter, though the air in it was renewed occasionally; the third group, similarly spread, was exposed to air having 80% relative humidity; the fourth, similarly spread, was exposed to oxygen in a wide-base bottle which was first evacuated and then filled with oxygen at the atmospheric pressure, the gas being renewed occasionally.

A representative sample was withdrawn from each group after different intervals of time for the determination of acid and base adsorption capacity, as shown below.

Acid Adsorption.—A sample of charcoal (0.5 g.) was shaken with 0.1 N-HCl solution (100 c.c.) for about 48 hours after which decrease in concentration was determined by titrating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid against a standard alkali solution in the usual manner.

Base Adsorption.—A charcoal sample (0.5 g.) was shaken with 100 c.c. of 0.2 N-Ba(OH)₂ solution (100 c.c.) for about 48 hours and the decrease in concentration was determined by titrating 20 c.c. of the clear supernatant liquid against a decinormal acid solution. This method has been shown (Puri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) to provide the maximum capacity of charcoal to neutralise alkalies.

Evacuation at 1000°.—The samples, which had been allowed to age in air and in closed bottles for a period of six months, were subjected to evacuation in a resistance tube furnace at 1000° and the gases evolved were analysed in the following sequence. Carbon dioxide was estimated by passing through a series of Erlenmeyer flasks containing a known amount of a standard barium hydroxide solution. Carbon monoxide and hydrogen in the rest of the gaseous mixture were estimated by exploding with a known excess of oxygen, followed by the measurement of contraction produced on cooling and on the introduction of potash solution.

The ultimate vacuum over charcoal on evacuation was of the order of 10^{-2} mm. of mercury.

The results of these experiments are shown in Tables I—IV. Acid adsorption by sugar charcoal as well as coconut shell charcoal was of the order of 20 m.e. per 100 g., which remained almost unchanged on ageing or on altering the temperature of carbonisation. These results therefore have not been included.

DISCUSSION

It is interesting to note, on reference to Tables III and IV, in the first instance, that the CO₂ equivalent of the alkali, neutralised by charcoal, is quite close to the amount of CO₂ evolved from it on high-temperature evacuation. This shows that the capacity of charcoal to neutralise alkalies is almost entirely due to the presence of CO₂ in the charcoal complexes. This view was confirmed by observing that the evacuated charcoals lost their base-neutralising capacity almost entirely. This is in conformity with the conclusions previously arrived at (Puri *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 219).

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TABLE I

Base-neutralising capacity of sugar charcoal prepared at different temperatures on ageing under different conditions.

Carbonisation temp.	Condition of ageing.	Ba(OH) ₂ (m.e.) neutralised after different intervals of time per 100 g. of charcoal								
		Initial	15 mins.	45 mins.	90 mins.	3 hrs.	6 hrs.	12 hrs.	3 days.	2 months.
350°	Free air	355.0	356.2	358.1	366.9	368.7	371.5	399.9	487.9	492.3
	Humid air	...	353.7	...	364.7	370.3	...	398.6	...	489.2
	Limited air	345.2	349.1	350.6	351.8	352.3	358.0	361.6	368.9	390.7
	Oxygen	395.5	436.1	468.3	479.1	492.8	492.3	494.1	493.9	495.5
400°	Free air	310.4	319.3	320.4	321.9	323.6	329.5	334.4	345.4	355.8
	Humid air	...	317.0	...	323.6	...	328.5	...	341.9	353.7
	Limited air	293.9	310.4	315.4	318.1	320.3	...	325.1	321.8	333.9
	Oxygen	314.3	328.7	330.0	355.8	358.6	357.9	359.0	358.3	358.2
500°	Free air	77.6	87.5	90.5	97.0	98.2	99.8	101.4	125.9	132.2
	Humid air	...	84.8	...	...	95.7	...	99.7	...	129.9
	Limited air	67.9	77.3	82.0	84.3	94.3	97.0	98.6	100.3	102.5
	Oxygen	103.0	121.6	126.7	129.6	129.7	...	130.0	129.8	129.9
600°	Free air	34.7	35.6	36.5	36.8	37.7	39.5	40.8	53.6	55.8
	Humid air	...	33.7	...	...	38.7	...	...	54.0	56.5
	Limited air	22.3	23.3	26.5	27.3	27.6	35.9	36.6	40.8	43.7
	Oxygen	41.3	43.6	48.5	51.3	53.4	54.0	54.9	55.2	55.3

TABLE III

Degassing of different samples of sugar charcoal at 1000*

Description of the samples.	CO ₂ equiv. of the alkali, neutralised by charcoal (cf. Table I.) (c.c. N.T.P./g.)	Amounts of gases evolved on evacuating at 1000° (c.c. N.T.P./g.).		
		CO ₂ .	CO.	* H ₂ .
1. Carbonised at 350° and exposed to free supply of air for 6 months.	55.13	55.33	92.35	101.98
2. Do, but exposed to limited supply of air for 6 months.	43.76	41.97	83.53	98.04
3. Carbonised at 400° and exposed to free supply of air for 6 months.	39.85	40.43	84.87	98.38
4. Do, but exposed to limited supply of air for 6 months.	37.39	36.75	75.21	99.75
5. Carbonised at 500° and exposed to free supply of air for 6 months.	14.80	15.18	79.78	98.87
6. Do, but exposed to limited supply of air for 6 months.	11.48	12.28	68.97	103.63
7. Carbonised at 600° and exposed to free supply of air for 6 months.	6.25	6.72	80.13	102.43
8. Do, but exposed to limited supply of air for 6 months.	4.89	5.02	69.89	98.43
9. Carbonised by sulphuric acid and exposed to oxygen.	68.10	68.48	87.32	105.34

* The samples of sugar charcoal were almost free of ash.

TABLE IV

Degassing of different samples of coconut shell charcoal at 1000°.*

Description of the samples.	CO ₂ equiv. of the alkali, neutralised by charcoal (cf. Table II) (c.c. N.T.P./g.)	Amounts of gases evolved on evacuating at 1000° (c.c. N.T.P./g.).		
		CO ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ .
1. Carbonised at 350° and exposed to free supply of air for 6 months.	57.50	54.29	77.95	83.25
2. Do, but exposed to limited supply of air for 6 months.	49.08	47.37	69.71	81.98
3. Carbonised at 400° and exposed to free supply of air for 6 months.	40.07	39.97	78.34	83.11
4. Do, but exposed to limited supply of air for 6 months.	29.94	28.76	71.54	84.32
5. Carbonised at 500° and exposed to free supply of air for 6 months.	36.89	37.34	76.76	78.06
6. Do, but exposed to limited supply of air for 6 months.	27.36	25.65	70.86	83.21

* The samples were rendered ash-free before degassing.

Thus, increase in the base-adsorption capacity (b. a.c.) of charcoal on ageing, as shown in Tables I and II, may be attributed to increase in the amount of the CO_2 -complex, and it may be inferred from these results (Tables I and II) that the surface oxidation of charcoal, leading to the formation of this complex, proceeds rapidly in oxygen, but only gradually in air. The change brought about by oxygen in six hours is almost the same as that brought about by air in about 6 months. The presence of moisture does not appear to have any effect on the rate of the amount of formation of the complex. However, if charcoal is allowed to age in a limited supply of air (as in closed bottles in the present experiments), surface oxidation takes place to a small extent only. It can be shown by simple calculations that oxygen contained in the air of the sealed bottles (half-pound capacity) is sufficient to bring about the small increase in the complex which has actually been observed to take place. Moreover, the bottles had to be opened occasionally while withdrawing the samples.

It is also evident (Tables I and II) that it is not possible to increase b.a.c. of charcoal beyond a certain limit even on prolonged exposure to oxygen, which shows that the amount of CO_2 - complex cannot increase beyond a certain maximum value on exposure to oxygen at ordinary temperatures.

Considering the rate of 'pick-up' of oxygen from free supply of air, it is seen that it is quite rapid to begin with, but it falls appreciably afterwards. It will be noted, for instance, that in several cases (Tables I and II) the value obtained after 12 hours' exposure to air, is as high as 70 to 80% of the maximum but in order to pick up the remaining 20 to 30% of the value, the samples have to be exposed to air for a period of about six months. It is also seen that even the 'initial' values are quite appreciable. It may be mentioned that these 'initial' values were actually determined on cooling charcoal to room temperature after its preparation at a particular temperature, and this naturally took a few minutes. The surface oxidation in the first few minutes therefore appears to be even more rapid.

The carbonisation temperature also seems to influence the formation of the CO_2 -complex appreciably. As the temperature rises, the base-neutralising capacity, initial as well as ultimate, determined on exposure to air or oxygen, decreases. The amount of CO_2 evolved also decreases (Tables III and IV) with increase in the carbonisation temperature. The amount of CO evolved, however, appears to be more or less independent of the carbonisation temperature although it is more in free air than in limited air. It appears that the CO_2 -complex, which is known to be less stable (Smith *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 298; Puri *et al.*, *Punjab University Res. Bull.*: 1956), is decomposed to a certain extent with rise in the carbonisation temperature and is not reformed easily on simple exposure to air or oxygen at ordinary temperatures, but the CO-complex, which is much more stable (*loc. cit.*), remains more or less unchanged up to 600° , which is the maximum temperature employed for carbonisation in these experiments.

A small amount of sugar charcoal was also prepared by bringing about the carbonisation with concentrated sulphuric acid. The mass was washed repeatedly with distilled water to free it completely from the sulphate ions. The capacity of

this charcoal for neutralising barium hydroxide was 608 m.e./100 g. after exposure to oxygen. The sample on evacuation also afforded the corresponding amount of CO_2 , as shown in Table III. It is evident that the amount of CO_2 -complex formed now is much greater. Probably the average carbonisation temperature was even less than 350° in this case. However, it is interesting to note that the amount of CO evolved remains almost unchanged, as expected. It might be argued that the treatment with sulphuric acid itself probably adds more oxygen which is eliminated as CO_2 . In order to verify this point, the samples carbonised at 350° and 400° were given similar treatments with sulphuric acid, followed by similar repeated washings with distilled water, but no increase in their base-neutralising capacities nor in the amount of gases evolved on evacuating at 1000° was noticed.

The results reported in Tables III and IV show incidentally that hydrogen also gets fixed up by charcoal to an appreciable extent and that this is given out in the free state on degassing at high temperatures. Its amount remains almost independent of the carbonisation temperature up to 600° . This is to be expected since hydrogen is known to be evolved from carbons in the temperature range of 900° - 1200° (Anderson and Emmett, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1947, 51, 1308; 1952, 56, 753; Puri et al., *Chem. & Ind.*, 1956, B. I. F. Review, 30).

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